

Interview with Anime Director Tensai Okamura at FicZone 2019

Andrés Domenech Alcaide

CoolJapan.es

In April 2019, we had the pleasure of meeting Tensai Okamura (Fukushima Prefecture, Japan, 1961) during his attendance at the FicZone + Granada Gaming + Meeple Factory event, held in the city of Granada. Okamura grew up in Kanagawa Prefecture and, after completing his studies at Waseda University (Tokyo)—where he developed his first animated short film alongside fellow students—he began a career in the animation industry that continues actively to this day. His first professional work was on the feature film *Lensman* (1984), where he started as an in-betweenner. Recognising his abilities, he soon began working on projects such as *Yawara!* (1989), an adaptation of the original manga by Naoki Urasawa.

He also worked as a director on several episodes of the original anime *Neon Genesis Evangelion* (1995), produced by GAINAX, which involved artists such as Yoshiyuki Sadamoto and Hideaki Anno.

Okamura has contributed storyboards to anime such as *Cowboy Bebop* (1998) and *Ghost in the Shell: Stand Alone Complex 2nd Gig* (2004), and has directed series including *The Seven Deadly Sins* (2014), based on the manga by Nakaba Suzuki, and *Kuromukuro* (2016). In the field of animated cinema, he worked as a key animator on films such as *My Neighbor Totoro* (1988), directed by Hayao Miyazaki, and the cult film *Jin-Roh: The Wolf Brigade* (2000).

He has also contributed as a director to animated sequences in video games such as *Tales of Destiny* (1997), *Wild Arms 2* (2000), and the PlayStation version of *Tales of Phantasia* (1998, re-released in 2000).

As we can see, Okamura has been involved in major productions and cult series that have achieved significant recognition both in Japan and in the West.

Interview with Tensai Okamura

Cool Japan: It is a pleasure to meet you, Mr. Okamura. To begin, we would like to ask you about your career. Have you always been interested in working in animation?

Tensai Okamura: To be honest, my interest in manga and animation dates back to my childhood.

CJ: You have worked with studios such as Madhouse, founded by the renowned Masao Maruyama. What can you tell us about the studio? Which project did you most enjoy working on there? Additionally, you have worked as a storyboard artist on anime such as *Cowboy Bebop* and *Ghost in the Shell: Stand Alone Complex 2nd Gig*, and have collaborated on projects such as *Neon Genesis Evangelion*, *Wolf's Rain*, and *My Neighbor Totoro*—all highly acclaimed both in Japan and internationally. What has the impact of these well-known projects meant to you?

TO: I am very happy that these works are so well known, especially outside Japan. At first, I was not really aware of it, but from time to time I am invited to different events. Still, it does not affect my daily life that much.

In my work on *The Seven Deadly Sins*, I always aimed to respect Nakaba Suzuki's great ability to convey dynamism and movement in his original manga, with the added difficulty that the visual format and contrast in manga differ from those in animation.

For example, there are vertically oriented panels in manga, whereas modern animation is presented in a widescreen format. You therefore have to translate that dynamism onto the screen and adapt it to a completely different format and proportions.

CJ: Your extensive experience in animation has led you to become a director yourself, as in the case of *The Seven Deadly Sins* (2014) and *Kuromukuro* (2016). Of all your roles, which is your favorite?

TO: At present, my favourite role is storyboarding. It is the work I feel most comfortable with—it comes most naturally to me.

The downside of writing and drawing storyboards is that, if you focus exclusively on that, you become somewhat detached from the frontline of animation production—actually drawing the images that will be animated. That is the negative aspect of this type of work. I enjoy being directly involved in the core of the production process, and that connection weakens if I focus solely on storyboards.

CJ: You have also worked on video games such as the PlayStation adaptation of *Tales of Phantasia*, *Tales of Destiny*, and *Wild Arms 2: 2nd Ignition*. What differences have you found working in this sector?

TO: When I first started working on video games, the sequences were quite short. Compared to working on a full anime series—or even a full season—it is a much shorter contribution in terms of duration.

The video game industry employs highly skilled and professional people. Everyone focuses on their specific role, and given the high level of expertise involved, the work progresses efficiently and at a very fast pace.

The team who interviewed Tensai Okamura —at the centre of the image—

CJ: It is often said that one of the most difficult tasks for an animator is adapting their personal style to the designs of other artists. What has this meant for you?

TO: Well... that is a very difficult question [thoughtful]. I can adapt to a style and replicate it faithfully—I am capable of doing so. But I always find myself wondering whether I should add something of my own, and why not do so. This applies not only to visual style, but also to narrative elements. When a manga is selected for adaptation, you cannot simply say, “I don’t like this part, I’ll change it because I feel like it,” nor can you think, “this part isn’t well done... I’ll improve it.”

You cannot alter the original work or its message on your own, although you may ask the author for permission—but generally speaking, this is not well regarded. What you must do instead is identify the strengths of an author’s style and the series itself, and then adapt the work based on that analysis. The goal is to focus on these elements and present the most impactful aspects of the work as effectively as possible.

A very illustrative example comes from a series I worked on, *Blue Exorcist* (2011). The protagonist’s father, Shirō Fujimoto, dies. For Rin Okumura, this is a key event that drives the story forward. The entire narrative arc revolves around this moment. To achieve that, it is not enough for the death to be impactful—you also need to create a bond with the audience.

In the manga, this happens quite quickly, but we felt that would be too abrupt in the anime. Since it is such a crucial moment at the beginning of the story, we wanted to show the relationship more clearly—shared memories and emotional connections with other characters. We could not simply have him appear and then die. We added several scenes featuring Shirō so that viewers would grow attached to him and feel the full weight of his death, as well as better understand the protagonist’s relationship with his father.

Adapting a manga requires carefully assembling its elements, because the audiovisual medium does not function in the same way. That is where the greatest difficulty lies. The first time I directed was very challenging, as I had to handle many responsibilities in addition to directing, such as storyboards.

In anime, we sometimes reach the same point in the story as the manga, and for various reasons we may also add extra content—additional episodes or new characters—because we want audiences to find something new in the adaptation. The goal is not to create a completely identical copy of the original manga.

When producing an anime, the most common approach is to adapt a manga, and the team must come together to determine which aspects are most important and should be emphasised. You have to identify what makes the work compelling and highlight those elements. *Blue Exorcist*, for me, was one of the most representative examples of this process.

CJ: We would be honoured if you could tell us a bit about your working methods. As an artist, which techniques do you prefer? Are you more inclined toward traditional media—pencil, paper, cels, and paint—or do you prefer modern digital tools?

TO: When it comes to digital art and new techniques, I still prefer working with traditional pencil and analogue tools. I enjoy drawing much more that way. My favourite tool is the pencil.

CJ: When creating storyboards, what references do you draw from in manga, animation, or cinema?

TO: I cannot give specific examples, but every film I watch becomes a tool that helps me generate new ideas.

CJ: Regarding *Kuromukuro*, one of your most recent productions, where did the idea for a series that combines samurai, aliens, oni, and mecha come from?

TO: It all began when I received a message from Kenji Horikawa, the producer of the series and founder of P.A. Works. He knew me from my work on *Medabots* (1999) for the studio Bee Train. He wanted to collaborate again on an original project to celebrate the studio's anniversary.

The studio is located near a large dam in Toyama, Japan—on the Kurobe River—and he said to me, “Do you remember the dam and where it is? Would you like to place a giant robot there?” That is how my involvement in the series began, and shortly after, I was already meeting with the animation team and the rest of the staff.

CJ: What can you tell us about your future projects? What are you currently working on?

TO: I am currently working on two projects—two films. I am in the early stages, figuring out how I will approach my work on them. I am also working on storyboards for two series. One of them is *Carole & Tuesday* (2019), which began airing in April, and the other is *Fairy Gone* (2019), directed by Kenichi Suzuki.

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank the press team of the CrossOver organisation for their assistance in conducting the interview, as well as for taking the photographs in which our colleague appears alongside Tensai Okamura and his interpreter, Ken Yamaya, to whom we also extend our gratitude for his excellent work.

We would also like to thank Tensai Okamura for his time, his kindness, and for granting us this interview.

Sources

- **Interview conducted by:** Andrés Domenech Alcaide [CoolJapan.es] |
Interview interpreted by: Ken Yamaya
- **Photographs by:** FicZone press team

Licence and Original Publication

- **Licence:** This article and its content are published under **CC BY 4.0**, which allows sharing and adaptation of the material provided that the source and author are credited
- *Originally published on CoolJapan.es on March 11, 2020*
—Entrevista a Tensai Okamura en FicZone 2019—
- *This version is a faithful translation into English by Andrés Domenech Alcaide*